

TURBIDITY DETECTION USING IMAGE PROCESSING

Dr. Inderdeep Verma¹, Aditi Sharma², Khushi Upadhyay³, Manjari⁴

¹Associate Professor, Department of CSE, IIMT College of Engineering, Greater Noida, UP
indervermaiimt0071@gmail.com

²U.G. Student, Department of CSE, IIMT College of Engineering, Greater Noida, UP
aditi.iimt@gmail.com

³U.G. Student, Department of CSE, IIMT College of Engineering, Greater Noida, UP
khushiu1101@gmail.com

⁴U.G. Student, Department of CSE, IIMT College of Engineering, Greater Noida, UP
manjarich23@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The motive behind this project is to design a technique to determine turbidity of water samples using image processing. Traditional method of turbidity detection implies various manual and heavy procedures. By using image processing, it can be done in a simple way and that too anywhere and anytime. The proposed technique consists of water sample images captured by HD camera and applying concepts of image processing to those captured images. This method is more reasonable and scientific.

KEYWORD: Image Processing, Turbidity, Turbidity-meter, RGB to Gray Conversion, Otsu Segmentation.

1. Introduction

Generally, Turbidity is the standard for measuring water quality for a variety of uses, from city's drinking water to monitoring aspects of the environment. If water has a high amount of turbidity, we'll be able to see it. Turbidity affects scattering of light as a result of material in the water. When gathering a sample, water with high turbidity looks cloudy. Turbidity may cause severely if not taken into consideration for example, blocking of filters and stop them from working effectively, filling of tanks and pipes with mud and silt, damaging valves and taps, etc. are the adverse effects of high turbidity. Water with high turbidity has an adverse effect on aquatic systems. When water sets full of sediments it affects marine life. Contaminated water can smother aquatic organisms. Sunlight can't get to aquatic plants. Not to mention, turbid water can carry microorganisms or harmful elements like mercury (Hg), lead (Pb), and bacteria. When it comes to drinking water, the health of the local population can be in danger when water has a high turbidity measurement. The risk of waterborne disease outbreaks increases when water contains high levels of contaminants. Whereas, low turbidity will avert the chlorine from killing the microbes in the water efficiently during the process of chlorination. Turbidity is the cloudiness or haziness of a fluid due to large numbers of particles that are either visible or invisible to the naked eye. The measurement of turbidity is one of the key tests of the water quality. It is calculated in the Nephelometric Turbidity unit abbreviated as NTU. If Turbidity is below 5 NTU, the water is pure. Among all the governance, testing of water quality, and in necessary measures against water pollution again, it is particularly important. For turbidity (one of the main indicators of water quality tests), detection is more important. This study presents a method for detecting turbidity of water based on the Image Processing theory.

2. Process

The technique of image processing will make it so easy. And we need only a good dataset of various samples of water in form of pictures. And by using algorithms of image processing, it can give direct

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measurement of turbidity in fraction of seconds. In the proposed method we capture an image of water of which turbidity is to be checked. Image processing techniques are used to detect the impurity present in the water sample. Comparison is done with the standard database to give final turbidity of water sample.

3. Algorithm

3.1. Input Image:

Image is captured using camera having minimum resolution of 620*850, which can be obtained using a digital camera of minimum 3 MP. This captured image is sent to the computer for further processing.

3.2. RGB to Gray conversion:

Colored image mainly consist of three components RED, GREEN, BLUE. The representation of a colour image using intensity function is done as shown below

$$IRGB = (fR * fG * fB) \quad (1)$$

Where $fR(m, n)$, $fG(m, n)$ and $fB(m, n)$ represents the intensities of the pixel (m,n) present in the red color band, Green color band and Blue color band respectively. The intensity of each color band can be stored using 8 bits, 16 bits but generally eight bits storage is preferred, which represents the quantization level 0 to 256. Gray levels are the representation of quantization levels done in gray scale image processing. Today, 8-bit storage methods are mostly preferred for storage. In an 8 bit gray scale image total 256 gray levels are present and pixels have intensity value from 0 to 255, where 0 represents black and 255 as white. The command to converts RGB images to grayscale is given by,

$$I = \text{rgbtogray}(\text{image}) \quad (2)$$

It operates by eliminating the hue and saturation information while retaining the luminance of an image.

3.3 Image Filtration:

As images are captured in real time, quality of an image gets affected due to many parameters of the surrounding which causes random variations in intensity and brightness, this random variation in image quality is called noise. There are different types of noises that occur during image processing, like impulse noise, salt and pepper noise, Gaussian noise.

In Salt and pepper noise black and white intensities occur randomly. Whereas, impulse noise represents random occurrence of white intensity levels.

But in Gaussian noise Gaussian distribution causes the intensity to vary randomly in an image. Linear smoothing filters are preferred to remove Gaussian noise and many other types of noises as well. Implementation of a linear filter is done by taking the weighted sum of the pixels in successive windows.

Generally, the pattern of weights that we use in each window is the same, which makes linear filters invariant.

Gaussian filter -It is mostly preferred filter for smoothing of a distorted image. The Gaussian kernel

uses certain properties of space-bandwidth products. The point spread function and transfer function for the continuous Gaussian filter is given below:

$$h(m, n) = g_{2D}(m, n) = (1/\sqrt{2\pi\sigma}) \exp^{-m^2/2\sigma^2} (1/\sqrt{2\pi\sigma}) \exp^{-n^2/2\sigma^2} \quad (3)$$

$$= g_{1D}(m) * g_{1D}(n) \quad (4)$$

3.4. Histogram:

The histogram of an image measures the number of pixels with a given gray or colour value. Histograms of colour images are not normally used, so we have plotted histogram of gray image only. Consider a grayscale image having N number of different intensity levels is provided, the intensity gray level histogram can be represented using a function,

$$h(g), \text{ where } g \in [0 \dots N] \quad (5)$$

where 0 to N are the intensity levels in the image or in the region of interest.

$$h(g) = N_g \quad (6)$$

N_g - Number of pixels in image or in the region of interest that have intensity level equal to g. The function obtained by normalizing histogram with the number of pixels in the image is called Probability Density Function (PDF) of the intensity levels.

$$p(g) = h(g)/M \quad (7)$$

Where M = image height x image width,
 PDF has following properties

$$P(g) \geq 0, \\ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p(g) dg = 1$$

3.5. Thresholding image:

This is a simple method of differentiating between an object and the background, which works provided they are of different intensities. Thresholding is the creation of binary images from gray images. It converts all pixels below threshold value to 0 and above threshold value to 1. If $B(x, y)$ is the gray version then to obtain a thresholded version $G(x, y)$ with threshold value T , G is set equal to 1 if $B(x, y) > T$ and zero otherwise. function used for thresholding is given by,

$$I = \text{graythresh}(\text{image}) \quad (8)$$

4. Observation

4.1- Input:

Fig 1: Input images

These are the images of water samples with varying turbidity level. These images are captured by high
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definition camera. Images will undergo different steps of image processing to get different required characteristics of an image like filtered image, gray image, gray contrast image, threshold image and many others.

4.2. Gray Scale Conversion:

Fig 2: Gray scaled contrast image

Fig.2 shows the contrast gray scale image of the input image having pixel intensity from 0 to 255. It is vital to have a good contrast to accurately capture information and better visualize features. Contrast is mainly depend on luminance and it is given by

$$\text{Contrast} = \frac{\text{Change in Luminance}}{\text{Average Luminance}}$$
$$\text{Contrast} = \frac{(\text{maxi}-\text{mini})}{(\text{maxi}+\text{mini})}$$

4.3. Thresholding of images:

Fig 3: Threshold images

Thresholding is the simplest method of segmenting images. To create binary images from gray scale images, we use this. When normalization of the pixel value occurs in between 0 and 1 then, it converts gray image into binary image which is obtained by converting each pixel below some threshold value to 0 and otherwise equal to 1. Blackish portion represents the turbidity in water sample and white or bright portion shows pure portion or less turbid in water sample. Image thresholding will help to detect the presence of any other kind of impurity present in water samples.

4.4. Histogram of input images:

Fig 4. Histogram of input image 1

Fig 5. Histogram of input image 2

Fig 6. Histogram of input image 3

Fig 7. Histogram of input image 4

Histogram shows the graphical representation of pixel intensity on Y-axis versus no. of pixels on X-axis. From histogram which is obtained experimentally it is shown that the no. of pixels are almost not varying and range is nearly between 200-250 in all four images as the comparison is based on the intensity of pixel. So, on comparing the pixel intensity value with a database which consists of a table having turbidity for given value of pixel intensity, we obtain final turbidity of samples.

5. Result

Data Set	Measured Turbidity	Detected turbidity
1	100	95
2	500	489
3	1000	1026
4	2000	2120

Table No. 1

The table shows the comparison between turbidity measured by traditional method and image processing method with their histogram values. In the table column 1 gives the number of input in the data set. Column 2 gives measured turbidity using traditional method, column 3 gives turbidity values detected by image processing method technique.

6. Conclusion

We get results in fraction of seconds by digital image processing method whereas laboratory method takes very much time and it's also expensive. Accuracy can be further increased by improving the camera quality, availability of samples of database and various other operations on the input images using digital image processing. So finally from this paper it can be concluded that Image processing technique is the best alternative method to traditional method for turbidity detection.

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AUTHORS

Dr. Inderdeep Verma, Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, IIMT Collage of Engineering, Knowledge Park III Greater Noida, UP, India, received his B.Tech. degree in Computer Science and Engineering from Punjabi University Patiala, Punjab, India in 2005 and M.Tech. degrees in Information Technology from, RGTU, Bhopal India in 2011. Ph.D. degree in Computer Science and Engineering at Dr. K.N. Modi University Newai, Rajasthan, India in 2018. He is member of Computer Society of India (CSI).

Aditi Sharma is pursuing her B.Tech. Degree from Department of Computer Science and Engineering, IIMT College of Engineering, affiliated by Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam Technical University batch (2017-2021)

Khushi Upadhyay is pursuing her B.Tech. Degree from Department of Computer Science and Engineering, IIMT College of Engineering, affiliated by Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam Technical University batch (2017-2021)

Manjari is pursuing her B.Tech. Degree from Department of Computer Science and Engineering, IIMT College of Engineering, affiliated by Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam Technical University batch (2017-2021)

